

Description of all files:

- **breaking-changes-cases-full-description.pdf**: this file contains all 55 unique breaking changes cases described. There are the description and links to changelog, issues, pull-requests, commits and diff.
- **results.py**: contains the scripts used in results. This file allow to reproduce the results for each RQ. However, to reproduce our results it require a lot of metadata package.json and repositories, so, this file may download over 2.5GiB in paths `packagejson/` and `workspace/`; the first one will save all metadata file package.json (51.0 MiB) and the second one will store the cloned repositories (2.5GiB).
- **all-cited.csv**: this file contains the name and the link to all packages and sites cited in our paper.
- **breaking-changes-cases.csv**: this file contains the whole data used to generate our results. Each line represents a breaking change case (64 cases). There are the follow fields:
 - **client_name**: the client that was impacted by that breaking change.
 - **provider_name**: the dependency tree from the client to provider package that raised the breaking change; the last package is the one that raised the breaking change.
 - **versions_impacted**: the amount of client's releases impacted by that breaking change.
 - **category**: the category of that breaking change.
 - **documentation**: all places that breaking change was documented. *Ichangelog* means the breaking change was documented in a changelog when it was introduced; *Fchangelog* means the breaking change was documented in a changelog when it was fixed.
 - **fixed_by**: which package that really fixed the breaking change first; both client and provider can fix a breaking change, but this field contains the one that fixed the breaking change first.
 - **fixed_client**: if the client fixed that breaking change, its name is in this field.
 - **fixed_provider**: if the provider fixed that breaking change, its name is in this field.

- **client_fix**: how the client fixed the breaking change: just changing the provider's version or changing its code.
- **client_version_introduced**: the first client's version that the breaking change manifested.
- **client_version_fixed**: the client's version that the breaking change did not manifest anymore.
- **provider_version_introduced**: the provider's version that the breaking change was introduced.
- **provider_version_fixed**: the provider's version that fixed the breaking change.
- **provider_was**: how the client changed the provider's version. Client package can update, downgrade, replace the provider and remove the provider.
- **impacted_by**: how the client was impacted by the breaking change: implicit, when the client got a breaking change because of a range of version or explicit, when the client updated manually the provider's version and got the breaking change.
- **range_change**: from which range and to which range the client changed the provider's version.
- **semver_intro**: in which semver level the breaking change was introduced.
- **semver_fixed**: in which semver level the breaking change was fixed.
- **breaking-changes-cases.json**: basically, the file `breaking-changes-cases.csv` into a json format that allows to analyze the data easily.
- **clients.csv**: this file contains the name, the amount of releases that the package had, the amount of releases we used in this study, the amount of providers in the latest package's release and the link of all client packages that we used in this study.
- **rq[1|2|3]_graph.R**: files used to create the graph. The data may be generated using the file `results.py`.
- **results.zip**: this file contains the script `install/test` results for all client's releases.